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Abstract submission

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Abstract : Background: Camera-based active and assisted living (AAL) technologies are an eminent solution to the accruing burdens of population ageing but are hardly accepted by older adults. The technology's privacy implications and perceived usefulness are established antecedents to its acceptance. However, one understudied barrier to acceptance is a failure in future self-identification. Specifically, to the extent that the wellbeing benefits of camera-based AAL technologies largely accrue to the future (rather than the present) self, older adults who have less (versus more) vivid impressions of their future selves may be less willing to accept the technology today. Objectives: To assess the unique contribution of future self-vividness to the prediction of older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. Methods: A cross-sectional online survey collected data from n = 183 community-dwelling older adults (mean age = 64.2, 51.9% male). Hierarchical logistic regression was used to evaluate the association of future self-vividness and acceptance, independent of demographics, privacy concerns, and the perceived usefulness of camera-based AAL technologies. Results: Future self-vividness was positively associated with an increased likelihood of acceptance (OR = 2.54, 95% CI 1.26-5.11) even after controlling for the effects of demographics, perceived usefulness, and privacy concerns. Compared to a demographics-only model (Nagelkerke R² = .256) and subsequent model that included privacy concerns and perceived usefulness as additional predictors (Nagelkerke R² = .439), the addition of future self-vividness added significantly to the prediction of acceptance ($\chi^2 = 7.58$, p = .006, Nagelkerke R² = .495). Conclusion: Acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies is uniquely influenced by future self-vividness. Enhancing the vividness with which older adults envisage their future selves may be an important strategy to promote acceptance and use of camera-based AAL technologies.

Key message 1 : Future self-vividness is uniquely associated with the acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies

Key message 2 : Interventions that enhance future self-vividness may promote acceptance of AAL technologies

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